

MEDICINAL SANO (CASSIA) TOUR L., CLASSIFICATION OF PLANT, CULTIVATION AGROTECHNICS AND APPLICATION IN MEDICINE

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Abstract. Resolution of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 10, 2020 "on additional measures for the development of folk medicine in the Republic of Uzbekistan" PP-4668" on measures to expand the scope of scientific research on the cultivation and processing of Medicinal Plants, the development of their seed production "dated November 26, 2020, PP-4901," protection of wild, based on the decisions of PP-4670 "on measures for processing and rational use of available resources", the Research Institute of genetic resources of plants, the Department of selection, seed and agrotechnics of medicinal plants, according to the 2023 work plan, enrichment of the insitiut gene pool, for the National genbank, medicinal sano (Cassia) Tourn L., it was planned to plant in a large experimental area to provide plant seeds.

Keywords: sano, xerophyte, kafiol, anthracsenin, sennazid A, sennazid V, senadae, glaxena, Cassia.

Classification of medicinal sano plant. The Sano plant is semi-shrub, reaching up to 1 m in height. Legumes are a genus of perennial grasses, shrubs or small trees belonging to the Fabaceae (Caesapiaceae) family. The STEM is branched, the branches at the bottom grow by touching the ground. The Leaf is complex, double-pubescent, with 5-10 pairs of thin petals: the flower is white or reddish, the inflorescences are pubescent. Pollen is 10, of which 3 are most often reduced. Basically, there are 500-600 species that grow in the tropics and subtropics (especially in America). Blunt-leaved, thin-leaved and sharp-leaved Sano has a medicinal property common in Arabia. Grown in Central Asia, Kazakhstan, Transcaucasia, southern Ukraine. The stems are branched, the lower branches grow creeping on the ground. The leaves are made up of 4-8 pairs of petals, a pair of feathers is complex, arranged in a row using a Bandy on the STEM and branches. The foliage is a plant with a pointed, pointed tip, an asymmetrical plate, with a flat edge. Its yellow flowers form a shingle inflorescences. The fruit is a flat, leafy ovoid, green-brown in color, multi-seeded legume. Blooms in June until autumn, fruiting is reached from September. The ick type of medicinal sano plant is: bay leaf sano-Cassia ostrolistnaya-(Cassia acutifolia Del) and thin-leaved sano-Cassia uzkolistnaya - (Cassia angustifolia Mill), and their leaf and fruit are used.

Geographical distribution. The medicinal sano species is native to the desert and semi-desert districts of Afirka and southern Arabia, Central Asia, Kazakhstan, the Caucasus and Bukhara region of Uzbekistan, Karakul, Qijduvan, Shafirikon districts, Kucichirchik, Piskent, Midshirchik districts of Tashkent region, the mechanical composition is light soils, on typical gray soils, is a drought-resistant xerophyte plant, mainly found in the thin-leaved sano - (Cassia angustifolia Mill) type, grown as an annual plant.

Agrotechnics of cultivation of Sano. Medicinal sano (Cassia) Tour L., the plant belongs to the legume family and is a semi-shrub plant that reaches up to 1m in height. The medicinal plant sano (Cassia) has xerophyte, light-loving and heat-loving properties. The Sano plant does not like

excessive humidification. It develops well when the soil temperature is 25-30°C. For Sano, it is recommended to plant on soils with a fertile, medium mechanical composition. Sano planting areas are driven out to a depth of 25-28 CM, giving 20-25 tons of organic fertilizer before the Earth is plowed in the fall.

It is not recommended to plant the medicinal sano plant in areas where legumes are planted. Because, the disease of legumes will be close to each other. In the spring before planting, the soil is carried out twice borona. In mid-April, seeds are sown when the soil temperature is 18-20°C at 20.04.2023. Before planting, the Sano's seed is processed in a low solution of sulfuric acid (in a 3:1 ratio) for 18-20 minutes, rinsed it in cold water and sewed to a depth of 2-3 cm on 70 cm egats. It will be advisable to spend an average of 8-10 kg of seeds of a medicinal sano plant per hectare of area.

Depending on this, the Department of selection, seed production and agrotechnics of medicinal plants, planting works are organized in small and large collection nurseries of the Institute. The medicinal sano is propagated from seeds, and the seeds germinate after 12-15 days.

The germination rate drops if the air temperature drops after planting the plant and there is a lot of moisture. And in areas with Spurs, the root is damaged by rot disease, and sprouted sprouts die off over time. After the emergence of sprouts, the field area is cultivated to a depth of 6-8 CM, weeded, yagana is done and watered. After the appearance of the stems, the plant is cultivated to a depth of 8-10 CM, the stems are loosened, weeded and fed with mineral fertilizers.

During the growing season, sanoni is watered 6-7 times, feeding on one hectare with 80-90 kg of nitrogen, 70 kg of phosphorus and 50 kg of potassium. Each fertilization is carried out before watering. After the medicinal raw materials of Sano are mowed, at a speed, the shade is dried in the place, and additional feeding of the areas where the plant is planted is recommended.

To be used. Medicinal sano preparations (tincture, dry extract, in the case of tablets, senadexin are included in the composition of complex sano tincture, poroshogi, general preparations) are used as a dragee. Prefabricated teas, kafiol and anthracsenin preparations used as Sano leaf surgi and in hemorrhoids are part of sennazid A and V, surgi preparations released in India-senadae, glaxena and other preparations. The Sano species is considered one of the medicinal plants that have been used since ancient times among the peoples of Central Asia to treat various diseases.

The tincture prepared on the leaf of Ibn Sina was used in the treatment of gout, bod, liver pain and yellow diseases, as well as as a surgi medicine. When you have a sore throat and swelling in the throat, it is used to gargle using a sano leaf tincture. In folk medicine, a decoction of the leaves and fruits of sano is used as a laxative for gastrointestinal diseases, especially in chronic constipation.

Preparation and use of the drug.

1. To prepare a tincture from Sano, 0.5 l of boiling water is placed in a container with a closed mouth, on which soy is dried in place, and 50-65 g of a leaf or fruit from pharmacies are placed and infused for an hour. Then strain through gauze and drink in the evening before going to bed, in a glass;

2. Soy is dried in place and taken 7-10 g from a leaf or fruit from pharmacies, placed in 100 ml of boiling water and infused for half an hour. Then it is passed through gauze and used 2-3 times a day in place of a tablespoon of the laxative drug;

3. Taking one of its dried leaves or one of its compounds from the pharmacy (it consists of pressed leaves, cut into 10 pieces, weighing 75 g in total), 2 pieces of it are placed in a glass of boiling water and placed in another container and boiled for 5 minutes. Then an hour is put. Then it is passed through gauze and drunk 2-3 times a day (depending on the condition) one tablespoon;

4. To prepare the decoction, put 5-10 g (1-2 tablespoons) of crushed leaves or 5 filter-bags in an enameled container, pour 100 ml (½ cup) of room temperature boiling water, close the lid and, stirring frequently, heat in a boiling water bath for 30 minutes, after complete cooling at room temperature, strain through gauze and squeeze the remaining raw materials (filter-packages are The volume of the resulting decoction is brought to 100 ml with boiled water. The decoction is stored in a cool place for a maximum of 2 days. One tablespoon is taken 1-3 times a day;

5. Side effects. Allergic reactions can be triggered in hypersensitivity;

6. Contraindications: can not be used in hypersensitivity to intestinal obstruction, acute inflammatory diseases of the gastrointestinal tract, compressed hernia, gastrointestinal and uterine bleeding.

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